

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MATHEMATICS TEACHING METHODS AND WAYS TO IMPROVE AND DEVELOP IT IN THE FUTURE

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Annotation: Arithmetic emerged as a subject long ago and has a strong place in school education. The method of teaching arithmetic was developed much later. Until the end of the seventeenth century, arithmetic did not exist as an independent textbook. The development of arithmetic teaching methods in Russia was organized under the direction of Peter I. The first general school in Russia, the School of Mathematics and Navigation, was instrumental.

Keywords: *history of teaching arithmetic, pedagogical technology, flexibility, practice.*

Arithmetic emerged as a subject very early on and has gained a clear and solid place in the home and school. The method of teaching it was developed much later.

By the 1960s, new disciplines began to emerge. A.I. In his book *Methodology*, Golderberg recommended the study of operations in three concentrations: a) decimal b) hundred d) multi-digit numbers.

He gave many methodological recommendations, such as arithmetic operations, their properties, explanatory explanations, arithmetic brush, and verbal calculation table. By the beginning of the twentieth century, there had been significant advances in the development and teaching of arithmetic. Arithmetic has proven to be at the forefront of mind development. Article 12 of the Law on Education states that "Primary education is aimed at forming the foundations of literacy, knowledge and skills required for general secondary education. Children are admitted to the first grade of school at the age of 6-7."

Indeed, at the threshold of the 21st century, the driving force behind the development of education is a pedagogical system that combines didactic issues and pedagogical technology.

Pedagogical technology is a field of knowledge through which radical changes will take place in the field of education in the 3rd millennium, the activity of teachers will be renewed, students' thirst for knowledge, love for the Motherland, love and humanity will be systematically formed. Let's clarify the concept of "technology". The word was introduced to science in 1872 in connection with technical progress and means Greek craft. The technological process always involves the execution of actions

in a certain sequence, using the necessary tools and conditions. Pedagogical technology is the process by which a teacher uses teaching aids to influence students in a particular setting, and as a result of this activity, the intensive formation of pre-defined personality traits in them. Theoretical and didactic aspects of pedagogical technology became the subject of research in the United States and the United Kingdom in the early 1980s. This is because the word "technology" in the broadest sense has been used to transfer theoretical knowledge to practical purposes, and to develop ways to copy specific ways of doing so.

The challenge - the leading quality attribute of modular learning technology - is flexibility. There are three types of flexibility: structural, meaningful, and technological.

Action is a collection of work done by a teacher to explain the elements of a lesson in the classroom and is part of the teaching process at this stage. If each subject is a separate stage, each of the elements of the subject can be considered as an action. First of all, it forms the basis of technology and is a key element in the development and implementation of educational goals. Actions consist of a number of methods, each of which is divided into actions.

Conclusion. The diagnostic nature of learning objectives in terms of the quality of acquisition of knowledge and skills requires the identification of the necessary levels of acquisition. The work of the modern teacher should be evaluated not from the point of view of a mere methodologist, but from the point of view of a "teacher-technologist".

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